

HOW CAN WE USE IT IN TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES?

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Annotation: This article discusses the advantages of using innovative and communicative information technology, which are the main factor in improving the quality of education and foreign language instruction. This article explores current issues of the use of information technology in teaching a foreign language. The introduction of new information technology in the educational process and in teaching a foreign language is an urgent requirement of today.

Key words: communicative skills, professional activity, summarization, electronic dictionaries

The purpose of learning a foreign language at the moment – is the development of communicative skills of the trainees, i.e. practical knowledge of a foreign language. Main purpose of the training is also a foreign language, which makes it suitable for oral and written communication, as in the future professional activity, and to further self-education. In combination with other competencies of foreign language communication competence training in the future will give each of the graduates the opportunity to be successful in the professional field and to fully realize their potential. And the task of the teacher is to educate a person the ability to communicate, to educate themselves. Necessary for the modern process of foreign language teaching is to create optimal conditions in order to make this process meaningful, effective and interesting for students. To this end, teachers use different methods and techniques that help to intensify the work of the students. In this invaluable assistance in this process renders the use of computer technology and Internet resources.

The specificity of the subject foreign language makes possible the use of computer technology in full in almost all these cases. When teaching grammar is very effective use of charts, tables, graphs, charts, drawings, and different ways of their projections (interactive whiteboard screens of personal computers, the printer is printing. Using computer technology possible in the study of almost any topic. If successful color scheme, using charts and tables, accompanied by voice (examples utterance in a foreign language) material will be perceived more easily and quickly, as will be used most of the receptors. Smaller will be the same amount of time in class, as will eliminate the need of recording material on the board. And with home PCs all training material can be stored on digital media (CD-, DVD- disks, flashcards) and transferred to a PC. Often there is

a problem of "ignorance of writing" of a word, and the use of computer technology this problem is completely eliminated. The computer can be effectively used for discovering new lexical material, new samples of statements. At the stage of consolidation and application of the generated knowledge and skills, the computer can be used in a wide variety of communicative tasks and situations on the basis of personality characteristics of the students. He can create the optimum conditions for the successful development of the program material , while ensuring adequate and feasible load for all students. Using Internet resources allows students to bring communication activities to reality, for example, view ads for buying and selling property in the study of the theme of "flat", the choice of a suitable theme for the guided tour "Free time. Travel ", etc. Meet and chat in the forums closer to the realities of the country's students studied language and enrich vocabulary idioms, slang expressions, vocabulary of contemporary youth.[8] Computer widely used as a means of exercising control over the activities of the trainees from the teacher, as well as a means of self-control. Computer testing can be used as a method of final or interim audit. Depending on the capabilities, students can be tested on personal computers in the local school network or the Internet. Fast results with this test allows the instructor to make timely adjustments to the educational process, to prevent lag, work individually with students.

When planning to use educational software and multimedia tools in study of a foreign language as well as other disciplines, it is necessary to consider the following aspects: - How will the program on students' motivation, their attitude towards the subject, increase or decrease the interest in it (for example, due to the difficult, unclear formulated requirements of the training program); - How the program meets the general thrust of the course; - Does the program promotes better absorption of the material, whether justified the choice of the proposed tasks, whether methodically supplied material; - Whether rationally designed using computer classes and new information technologies, provided there is enough time to perform independent work; - Do all students have the skills and abilities of your computer.

A common mistake when using computer technology in the learning process is permanent seat trainees at the computer. Need a variety of forms of educational activities. This front and work on updating knowledge, and group or pair work students on mastering specific skills training, and educational games, oral and written assignments . All of them should be arranged so that the computer does not become an end in itself, but merely a logical and very effective complement

to the educational process. Need to introduce new information technology throughout the education system and foreign language teaching in particular - is a pressing demand today. Here we have in mind not only the most modern technical equipment and new forms and methods of teaching, but also a completely new approach to the learning process, which helps to implement the principle of interactive, communicative- based learning provides individualization and differentiation based on features of trainees, their level and inclination.

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